

WHAW - WOMEN'S HEALTH AWARENESS WEEK

The Bioinfo4Women programme in collaboration with the BSC departments invites you to participate in the **Women's Health Awareness Week (WHAW)**. WHAW's aims to share the knowledge developed by BSC researchers on the subject with all its employees, visitors and collaborating institutions. We believe that it is a matter of vital importance that concerns us all and that it acquires particular relevance in these times of pandemic.

Agenda:

All week long:

1. WHAW Quiz - How much do you know about health in women and men?_

The [WHAW Quiz](#) consists of a **ten-question questionnaire** about women's and men's health and sex differences. The quiz is **open to all BSC employees regardless of previous experience**. Participants will increase their knowledge during the quiz journey. The quiz winner will receive the book "Unwell Women: A Journey Through Medicine" during **the award ceremony during the closing session on the terrace**.

- Open: Monday 23 May at 10h
- Closes: Friday 27 May at 10h
- Format: Online
- Link: <https://bsc3.typeform.com/WHAWquiz>

2. BSC research posters about Health and Women

A series of posters showcase eight BSC research projects related to health. Visit the **poster's gallery displayed in the totem placed in the BSC-Repsol building's reception** during the whole week. On Friday, presenters will have the opportunity to explain the posters and related research during the **closing session of the activities on the terrace on Friday, May 27th**.

- Open: Monday 23 May at 10h
- Close: Friday 27 May at 14h
- Place: Totem in the reception BSC - Repsol Building

Wednesday 25th May

1. Webinar in collaboration with Sistema Navarro I+D+i en Salud. Jornada de Investigación en Salud con Dimensión de Género

- Title: “Jornada de Investigación en Salud con Dimensión de Género”.
- Speaker: Maria Jose Rementeria and Davide Cirillo (BSC-Life Dept.)
- Date: Wednesday 25 May
- Time: 10:00h – 12:00h (10:30h B4W talk)
- Place: U. Navarra
- Registration Link: <https://forms.gle/F8GvtLtcDvwDuP377>

2. CineForum

The CineForum on Women's Health aims to open an internal **dialogue** among BSC employees about the subject. The activity will start watching the video "**Dona, vostè no té**s" to continue with a moderated conversation by Nataly Buslón, BSC HR & Equity, Diversity and Inclusion Officer. The language of the video is Catalan and Spanish with English subtitles. The discussion will be moderated in English.

- Speaker: Maria Jose Rementeria and Davide Cirillo (BSC-Life Dept.)
- Date: Wednesday 25 May
- Video: “Dona, vostè no té res”. A documentary film about sex and gender bias in medicine <https://www.ccma.cat/tv3/alcanta/sense-ficcio/dona-voste-no-te-res/video/6146129/>
- Time: 16:00h – 17:30h
- Room: Severo Ochoa, Repsol Building

Wednesday 26th May

Seminars about Health and Women

Series of seminars (hybrid) on the subject, introduced by Alfonso Valencia including two talks:

1.1. “Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence for Health”.

- Speaker: [Davide Cirillo](#), Life Sciences Department, BSC.
- Date: Thursday 26 May
- Time: 12:00h – 12:30h
- Place: BSC – Repsol, Floor 1, room 1-3-2
- Remote Link: <https://www.youtube.com/user/BSCCNS>
(<https://youtu.be/dmLtMBwHG0c>)

1.2. “Sex and Gender Differences in Brain and Mental Health. Selected use cases on how to tackle them”.

- Speaker: [Simona Mellino](#), Women’s Brain Project
- Date: Thursday 26 May
- Time: 12:30h – 13:00h
- Place: BSC – Repsol, Floor 1, room 1-3-2
- Remote Link: <https://www.youtube.com/user/BSCCNS>
(<https://youtu.be/dmLtMBwHGOc>)

1.3. "La perspectiva de sexo y género en la ciencia e investigación biomédica para mejorar la medicina de precisión". Webinar in collaboration with Pasteur Institute of Uruguay.

- Chair: Victoria Prieto
- Speakers: Nataly Buslón (BSC-HR) & Davide Cirillo (BSC-Life)
- Date: Thursday 26 May
- Time: 14:30h - 15:30h
- Language: Spanish
- Place: Instituto Pasteur Uruguay
- Link YouTube: tube.pasteur.uy/live

Thursday 27th May

Closing session:

As a grand finale, the WHAW will close its activities on the terrace **awarding** the prize to the **WHAW Quiz winner, presentations of the research posters** and a get together with a **pica-pica**.

- Quiz Prize & Poster session
- Date: Friday 27 May
- Time: 13:00h – 14:00h
- Place: BSC-Repsol Building Terrace